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Microstructural characters of stridulitrum of selected Scutelleridae (Heteroptera: Pentatomoidea)

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Abstract: Microstructural aspects of sternal stridulatory vittae of eighteen scutellerid species were examined using the scanning electron microscope. Characters of microsculpture of the areas are presented and compared. Possible taxonomic significance of these structures is briefly discussed.

Key words: Hemiptera, Heteroptera, Scutelleridae, stridulation, stridulatory vittae, stridulatory area, microstructures.

Introduction

Sound producing structures are variously developed in several Heteropterous families (HANDLIRSCH 1900, LESTON 1954, 1957, USINGER 1954, GOGALA 1984, 2006). Such structures are usually composed of stationary portion (*strigil*, *stridulitrum*) and movable parts (*plectrum*) (SCHUH & SLATER 1995). Within Scutelleridae at least three different mechanisms of stridulation are described: *sternal strigil – tibial plectrum*, *hind wing strigil – tergal plectrum*, *pygophoral strigil – phallic plectrum* (LESTON 1954, SCHAEFER 1980, TSAI *et al.* 2011).

The sternal *strigil – tibial plectrum* mechanism is found in members of subfamilies Hoteinae, Pachycorinae and some Odontotarsinae. These Scutellerids have stridulatory vittae located on the IV-V (V-VII) sternites and plectrum consisting series of tubercles or setae positioned on the hind tibiae.

The aim of this study is to present the variability of microstructure of abdominal strigil areas in selected species of subfamilies: Hoteinae, Pachycorinae and Odontotarsinae. Additionally representatives of subfamily Eurygastrinae and Tectocorinae were examined to compare the microstructures of the sternal abdominal areas.

Material and methods

The study is based on specimens of 18 scutellerid species representing five subfamilies. The classification of the family is that presented by TSAI *et al.* (2011).

The list of material examined is presented below.

Pachycorinae AMYOT et SERVILLE, 1843

1. *Agonosoma trilineatum* (FABRICIUS, 1781) [Venezuela, Caracas, ZMHB]
2. *Ascanius hirtipes* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1835) [Brasil, ZMHB]
3. *Camirus conicus* (GERMAR, 1839) [Brasil, Bahia ZMHB]
4. *Diolcus variegatus* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1836) [South America, ZMHB]
5. *Missipus variabilis* (SPINOLA, 1852) [Chile, Santiago, ZMHB]
6. *Pachycoris klugi* BURMEISTER, 1835 [Mexico, ZMHB]
7. *Polytes obscurus* (DALLAS, 1851) [Bolivia, La Paz, ZMHB]
8. *Tetyra pinguis* GERMAR, 1837 [Brasil, Rio, ZMPB]
9. *Trichothyreus vitticeps* (STÅL, 1870) [Puerto Rico, ZMHB]

Hoteinae CARAPEZZA, 2009

10. *Deroplax nigropunctata* (STÅL, 1864) [Uganda, Ngowa, RBINS]
11. *Deroplax nigrofasciata* DISTANT, 1898 [Burundi, Rutana RMCA]
12. *Hotea acuta* STÅL, 1864 [Congo, Brazaville, MNHN]
13. *Hotea curculionoides* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1836) [Java, Bogor, MZPW]

Odontotarsinae MULSANT et REY, 1865

14. *Psacasta exanthematica conspersa* GERMAR, 1839 [Bosnia & Herzegovina, Zitomislac, ZHMB]
15. *Odontotarsus callosus* HORVATH, 1896 [Spain, Sierra de Guadarrama, ZMHB]

Eurygastrinae AMYOT et SERVILLE, 1843

16. *Eurygaster maura* (LINNAEUS, 1758) [Poland, Lower Silesia, DBUO]
17. *Eurygaster testudinaria* (GEOFFROY, 1785) [Poland, Lower Silesia, DBUO]

Tectocorinae MC DONALD et CASSIS, 1984

18. *Tectocoris dioptthalmus* (THUNBERG, 1873) [New Caledonia, MZPW]

The abdominal sternites of air-dried specimens were cleaned in 70% alcohol, coated with gold-palladium (20mA) and examined with a scanning electron microscope at 20 kV.

Material for this study was provided by the following institutional collections (with abbreviations used in the text): **DBUO** – Department of Biosystematics, University of Opole, Poland; **RBINS** – Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Brussels, Belgium; **MNHN** – Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France; **RMCA** – Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale, Tervuren, Belgium; **ZMHB** – Zoological Museum, Humboldt University, Berlin, Germany; **MZPW** – Zoological Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland.

Results

Description:

Microstructures of abdominal sterna consisting the stridulatory area are variable within examined groups of Scutelleridae. Different shape of sternal surface is observed in central part of sternites (area between the stridulatory vittae), stridulatory fields and lateral (marginal)

parts of the sternites. Descriptions of the variability of these structures of 18 Scutelleridae species are given below.

Pachycorinae AMYOT et SERVILLE, 1843

Agonosoma trilineatum (FABRICIUS, 1781) (Figs. 4a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel, coarse carinae composed of small elongate tubercles, single carinae bifurcated; marginal sternal surface with deep, round setigerous punctures and tile-like structures.

Ascanius hirtipes (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1835) (Figs. 5a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel, sharp carinae, bifurcated and anastomosing; marginal sternal surface mostly psilate with isolated, deep, round setigerous punctures.

Camirus conicus (GERMAR, 1839) (Figs. 1, 6a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located and single round punctures; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel, sharp carinae, single carinae bifurcated and anastomosing; marginal sternal surface rough with numerous, deep, round setigerous punctures.

Diolcus variegatus (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1836) (Figs. 7a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel, sharp carinae, mostly bifurcated and anastomosing; marginal sternal surface almost psilate with single, deep, round setigerous punctures.

Missipus variabilis (SPINOLA, 1852) (Figs. 2, 8a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located and single round punctures; the stridulatory area rough, covered by rows of elongate tubercles; marginal sternal surface rough with numerous, deep, round setigerous punctures.

Pachycoris klugi BURMEISTER, 1835 (Figs. 9a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel, distinctive and sharp carinae, bifurcated and anastomosing; marginal sternal surface rough with numerous, tile-like structures and single, deep, round setigerous punctures.

Polytes obscurus (DALLAS, 1851) (Figs. 10a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel, coarse carinae composed of small elongate tubercles, carinae often anastomosing and bifurcated; marginal sternal surface almost psilate with deep, round setigerous punctures.

Tetyra pinguis GERMAR, 1837 (Figs. 11a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel, distinctive and sharp carinae, bifurcated and anastomosing; marginal sternal surface rough with numerous, tile-like structures and single, deep, round setigerous punctures.

Trichothyreus vitticeps (STÅL, 1870) (Figs. 12a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel sharp carinae often anastomosing

and bifurcated; marginal sternal surface almost psilate with deep, round setigerous punctures.

Hoteinae CARAPEZZA, 2009

Deroplax nigrofasciata DISTANT, 1898 (Figs. 13a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel sharp carinae often anastomosing and bifurcated; marginal sternal surface rough with numerous, tile-like structures and deep, round setigerous punctures.

Deroplax nigropunctata (STÅL, 1864) (Figs. 14a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel sharp carinae anastomosing and bifurcated; marginal sternal surface rough with numerous, tile-like structures and deep, round setigerous punctures.

Hotea acuta STÅL, 1864 (Figs. 15a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located; the stridulatory vittae with almost parallel sharp carinae anastomosing and bifurcated; marginal sternal surface with, tile-like structures and round setigerous punctures.

Hotea curculionoides (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1836) (Figs. 16a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; nearly regularly located and single round punctures; the stridulatory area rough, covered by rows of elongate tubercles; marginal sternal surface rough with numerous, deep, round setigerous punctures.

Odontotarsinae MULSANT et REY, 1865

Psacasta exanthematica conspersa GERMAR, 1839 (Figs. 17a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size and single round punctures; the stridulatory area rough, covered by numerous, elongate tubercles, regular carinae not formed; marginal sternal surface rough with numerous, deep, round setigerous punctures.

Odontotarsus callosus HORVATH, 1896 (Figs. 18a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size and single round punctures and setae; the carinate stridulatory area not formed; marginal sternal surface rough with distinctive tile-like structures and numerous, deep, round setigerous punctures.

Eurygastrinae AMYOT et SERVILLE, 1843

Eurygaster maura (LINNAEUS, 1758) (Figs. 19a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size and single round punctures; the carinate stridulatory area not formed; marginal sternal surface rough with numerous round tubercles and deep, round setigerous punctures.

Eurygaster testudinaria (GEOFFROY, 1785) (Figs. 3, 20a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size and single round punctures; the carinate stridulatory area not formed; marginal sternal surface rough with numerous round tubercles and deep, round setigerous punctures.

Tectocoris diopthalmus (THUNBERG, 1873) (Figs. 21a-c)

Central sternal surface covered by numerous small teeth, similar in size; single round punctures present; the carinate stridulatory area not formed; marginal sternal surface wrinkled with small tubercles and single setigerous punctures.

Discussion

The results of this study show that microsculpture of stridulatory area is diversified in Scutelleridae. Most of the examined specimens have stridulatory area arranged as carinate fields located in medio-lateral parts of sternites but details of microsculpture can be different in shape. There are three basically different types of microsculpture. The carinae type may be sharp and almost parallel with bifurcated branches. The second type presents more irregular carinae composed of elongated tubercles. Type III with sternal microsculpture not formed as carinate structures.

The type I (Fig. 1) of carinae is the most frequently occurring type of microsculpture in Pachycorinae and Hoteinae. Nine of the examined species of these subfamilies (*Ascanius hirtipes*, *Camirus conicus*, *Diolcus variegatus*, *Pachycoris klugi*, *Tetyra pinguis*, *Trichothyreus vitticeps*, *D. nigropunctata*, *D. nigrofasciata*, *Hotea acuta*) have stridulatory area with well developed, sharp, almost parallel carinae.

The type II (Fig. 2) observed in four of studied species: *Agonosoma trilineatum*, *Missipus variabilis*, *Polytes obscurus*, *Hotea curculionoides*. It is characterized by presence of tuberculate carinae. The strigil areas are distinguished from the adjacent sternal parts.

The type III (Fig. 3) represents examined species with sternal microstructures not formed as the regular carinate area and not distinguished from the rest of sternal parts. These type is visible in species representing subfamilies Odontotarsinae (*Psacasta exanthematica conspersa*, *Odontotarsus callosus*) Eurygastrinae (*Eurygaster maura*, *E. testudinaria*) and Tectocorinae (*Tectocoris diopthalmus*).

Microstructure of central sternal parts (area between the stridulatory vittae) is very similar among studied scutellerids. The surface is covered by numerous microstructures resembling small, more or less sharp teeth and round punctures.

Marginal parts of sternites are most variable as far as concern the microstructures. The surface may be smooth or wrinkled and covered by numerous tubercles, tile-like structures and hair-bearing punctures. Between the marginal, strigil and central parts of sternite connecting zone is observed where the mixed microstructures are visible.

This study confirm the microsculpture of stridulatory vittae in Scutelleridae is variously developed in observed taxa. Presence of stridulatory vittae was the main diagnostic feature for subfamily Pachycorinae. Within this subfamily most often the type I of microsculpture is observed but not uniformly for the entire of the subfamily. Microsculpture of three of the examined species is different and represents the type II. Similar situation is within the Hoteinae, where the microsculpture pattern is not the same for all of the studied species. One of examined hoteins species has type II of microsculpture. It may suggest this morphological character could evolved independently and should not be regarded as the main taxonomic aspect determining these subfamilies. The evolution of these structure seems to be more complicated and should be supported by wider studies.

However the preliminary results of this analysis can be used as the significant data for constructing the classification system of entire of the family Scutelleridae.

Figs. 1–6. Microstructures of abdominal sterna. 1 –Type I of microstructures: *Camirus conicus* (GERMAR, 1839); 2 – Type II of microstructures: *Missipus variabilis* (SPINOLA, 1852); 3 – Type III of microstructures *Eurygaster testudinaria* (GEOFFROY, 1785); 4 – *Agonosoma trilineatum* (FABRICIUS, 1781); 5 – *Ascanius hirtipes* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1835); 6 – *Camirus conicus* (GERMAR, 1839); (a – central part of abdominal sterna, b – stridulatory area of abdominal sterna, c –lateral part of abdominal sterna, enlarged).

Figs. 7–10. Microstructures of abdominal sterna. 7 – *Diolcus variegatus* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1836); 8 – *Missipus variabilis* (SPINOLA, 1852); 9 – *Pachycoris klugi* BURMEISTER, 1835; 10 – *Polytes obscurus* (DALLAS, 1851); (a – central part of abdominal sterna, b – stridulatory area of abdominal sterna, c – lateral part of abdominal sterna, enlarged).

Figs. 11–14. Microstructures of abdominal sterna. 11 – *Tetyra pinguis* GERMAR, 1837; 12 – *Trichothyreus vitticeps* (STÅL, 1870); 13 – *Deroplax nigropunctata* (STÅL, 1864); 14 – *Deroplax nigrofasciata* DISTANT, 1898; (a – central part of abdominal sterna, b – stridulatory area of abdominal sterna, c – lateral part of abdominal sterna, enlarged).

Figs. 15–18. Microstructures of abdominal sterna. 15 – *Hotea acuta* STÅL, 1864; 16 – *Hotea curculionoides* (HERRICH-SCHAEFFER, 1836); 17 – *Psacasta exanthematica conspersa* GERMAR, 1839; 18 – *Odontotarsus callosus* HORVATH, 1896; (a – central part of abdominal sterna, b – stridulatory area of abdominal sterna, c – lateral part of abdominal sterna, enlarged).

Figs. 19–21. Microstructures of abdominal sterna. 19 – *Eurygaster maura* (LINNAEUS, 1758); 20 – *Eurygaster testudinaria* (GEOFFROY, 1785); 21 – *Tectocoris diophthalmus* (THUNBERG, 1873); (a – central part of abdominal sterna, b – stridulatory area of abdominal sterna, c –lateral part of abdominal sterna, enlarged).

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